

Beam-focusing Based Hierarchical Localization and Tracking in Angle and Range

Giorgos Stratidakis, Sotiris Droulias, Angeliki Alexiou
Department of Digital Systems, University of Piraeus, Piraeus 18534, Greece
Emails: {giostrat,sdroulias,alexiou}@unipi.gr

Abstract—Localization with high resolution is an essential application for use in future wireless networks, where the antennas are expected to be highly directional and therefore vulnerable to misalignment. Beam-forming with antenna arrays is already widely used, and can be used to estimate the direction of the receiver. The characteristic of beam-focusing to concentrate the power of a beam on a small area can be used to estimate the transmitter-receiver distance, and in cooperation with beam-forming, estimate the receiver location. This paper introduces a novel hierarchical localization algorithm that employs an original ranging hierarchical method that along with beam-tracking can be used to estimate the location of mobile users with adjustable resolution. The performance of the localization algorithm is presented through the probability of successful estimation, the average localization error, and the CDF of the localization error. Through various examples, it is demonstrated that the algorithm can achieve cm-level accuracy.

Index Terms—Large antenna arrays, Beam-forming, Beam-focusing, THz, tracking, ranging, localization, near-field

I. INTRODUCTION

Localization is becoming increasingly relevant for wireless communications as antennas become more directional and more susceptible to misalignment. However, conventional localization methods usually do not achieve the necessary resolution and, additionally, require extra equipment. Therefore, the development of new methods that offer high resolution and can function with the same equipment as the communication system is necessary. To this end, the concept of integrated sensing and communication (ISAC) has been introduced in an attempt to unify the sensing and communication systems and reduce both hardware and software requirements [1].

There are several works on localization where the authors estimate the location of the receiver, such as [2]–[9]. In [2], the authors, in an experiment, utilize the characteristics of the multipath environment to estimate the receiver (RX) location with 5.7 cm average localization error at 28 GHz, and 6.3 cm at 140 GHz. In [3], a localization scheme was presented where three

transmitters (TXs) cooperate to estimate the user equipment (UE) location with deep learning, and achieve an average localization error of ~ 24 cm. The authors in [4] employed chipless RFID systems that operate in the THz band to offer mm-level localization resolution with the help of dielectric resonator-lens tags. In [5], the authors presented a hierarchical method localization for beam training in multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO) systems that operate in the near-field. The authors in [6] derived the Fisher-information matrix and Cramer-Rao lower bounds for localization with large intelligent surfaces (LISs). Moreover, in [7], a deep neural network-based algorithm to estimate the user's location and maximize the received power at their location was presented. In [8], the authors used an received signal strength-based technique to estimate the user's location with reconfigurable intelligent surfaces. The authors in [9], the authors proposed a localization algorithm based on off-grid atomic norm minimization followed by a root multiple signal classification (r-MUSIC) algorithm that achieves cm-level accuracy. However, the complexity of the r-MUSIC algorithm is high, making it potentially unsuitable for localizing mobile users.

In this work, a novel hierarchical localization algorithm for mobile user tracking is presented. The algorithm takes advantage of the beam-forming characteristics to estimate the RX direction in relation to the TX broadside, and the characteristics of beam-focusing to estimate the TX-RX distance using a novel hierarchical ranging method. Beam-forming with antenna arrays is already widely used, and beam-focusing can be performed by adjusting the phase shifts of the antenna array. Therefore, the proposed algorithm can be performed with the same equipment as the communication systems, assuming it employs large enough antenna arrays, making it suitable for ISAC. The performance of the algorithm is demonstrated with the probability of success, the average localization error, and the empirical CDF of the localization error as a function of the number of timeslots (or samples) through Monte-Carlo simulations.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

The system model consists of one TX, and one mobile RX. The TX is a large antenna array (LAA)

This work was supported by the European Commission's Horizon Europe Programme under the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking TERA6G project (Grant Agreement 101096949) and INSTINCT project (Grant Agreement 101139161)

Fig. 1. System model. (a) The LAA performs beam-focusing at focal distance, d_f , and angle θ_r . (b) The beam footprint is depicted with a density plot, and is contained entirely in the TX panel.

capable of performing both beam-forming and beam-focusing, as shown in Fig. 1. The received power at the RX is given by

$$P_r = S_r A_r, \quad (1)$$

where $A_r = G_r \lambda^2 / 4\pi$, and G_r are the effective aperture and the antenna gain of the receiver, and λ is the wavelength. Moreover, the power density distribution of

the focused beam is calculated as

$$S_r(x, z) = \frac{2P_t}{\pi w^2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{z}{f_0 \cos \theta_r}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{2z}{kw^2 \cos \theta_r}\right)^2}} \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{z}{f_0 \cos \theta_r}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{2z}{kw^2 \cos \theta_r}\right)^2 \left(\frac{1}{\cos \theta_r}\right)^4}} \times \exp \left[-\frac{2(x \cos \theta_r - z \sin \theta_r)^2}{w^2 \left(\left(\cos \theta_r - \frac{z}{f_0}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{2z}{kw^2 \cos^2 \theta_r}\right)^2 \right)} \right], \quad (2)$$

where P_t is the transmitted power, w is the radius of the beam-footprint on the LAA, θ_r is the angle of the beam on the xz -plane, f_0 is the input wavefront curvature of the beam (i.e. at the LAA), and k is the wavenumber. When $f_0 \rightarrow \infty$ the wavefront becomes planar, and the TX performs conventional beam-forming. Assuming a specific f_0 along the direction $\theta_r = 0$, the maximum power occurs at focal distance [10], [11]

$$d_f = \frac{f_0}{(f_0/z_R)^2 + 1}, \quad (3)$$

where $z_R = kw^2/2$ is the Rayleigh distance, and k is the wavenumber. For relatively large footprints, where $z_R \gg f_0$, the focal distance, d_f , becomes equal to f_0 . The focal distance d_f marks the center of the focal area that takes the shape of an ellipse along the beam direction. The major radius of the 3dB focal area in the direction $\theta_r = 0$ is calculated as [11]

$$r_{max} = \frac{f_0}{(f_0/z_R)^2 + 1} \frac{f_0}{z_R}. \quad (4)$$

The size and position of the 3-dB focal areas are essential to the division of the radial distance that helps achieve the desired localization accuracy, which is determined by the size, and more specifically, the major radius, r_{max} of the ellipse along the TX-RX direction. Note that since d_f and r_{max} are entirely controlled by f_0 and w , the radial distance can be partitioned to any number of ellipses, the only limitation being the size of the LAA in relation to the focal distance. For a fixed w the size of the focal area increases as f_0 increases. Therefore, in order to form equally sized ellipses that guarantee fixed localization resolution at different distances, it is necessary that each 3-dB focal area is formed with a different beam-footprint on the TX. In the case of $f_0 \ll z_R$, the footprint, in practice, changes in proportion to f_0 for a fixed value of r_{max} . The input wavefront curvature for a focal area of focal distance, d_f , and major radius, r_{max} , is

$$f_0 = d_f \left(\left(\frac{r_{max}}{d_f} \right)^2 + 1 \right). \quad (5)$$

Fig. 2. Concept of the proposed localization algorithm. In Phase 1 the algorithm estimates the direction of the RX with beam-forming, and in Phase 2 the distance with beam-focusing. The dark-toned beams, and focal areas are the ones used (for this RX location) by the algorithm, while the light-toned beams and focal areas represent the rest of the beams and focal areas that can be generated by the codebooks. The dark outline marks the beams and focal areas where the user was found.

Moreover, the radius of the beam footprint on the TX for the same focal area is

$$w = \sqrt{2 \frac{r_{max}^2 + d_f^2}{kr_{max}}}. \quad (6)$$

To generate focal areas with the desired major radius at the desired focal distance, and therefore control the resolution of the localization algorithm, Eqs. (5) and (6) are used with Eq. (2).

III. HIERARCHICAL LOCALIZATION ALGORITHM

Exhaustive search with beam-focusing is time and resource consuming, especially with small focal areas. The proposed algorithm, simplifies the process by splitting it into two phases as shown in Fig. 2. In Phase 1, the TX performs beam-tracking to estimate the direction of the RX, and in Phase 2 it performs an hierarchical ranging approach based on beam-focusing to estimate the TX-RX distance. Each phase utilizes a binary tree-structured codebook. Assuming that the beam-tracking codebook has a total of L_t levels, and the ranging codebook, L_r levels, each phase requires $2L_t$, and $2L_r$ scans respectively to search the entire area. In Phase 1, the area of interest is divided in two angular sectors. Each sector is then divided in two smaller sectors, and each of them in two even smaller sectors. This process continues until the last level of the codebook. Phase 2 follows the same process with radial sectors along the direction estimated in Phase 1. Although in this paper the use of an LAA is assumed, the algorithm can also be performed with an access point (AP), and a LIS as

shown in [12]. In this case, the AP transmits to the LIS which in turn redirects or focuses the beam to the desired direction/location.

A. Phase 1: Beam-training

In this work, the beams provided in [13] were used to fill an hierarchical codebook, where the number of active elements is adjusted through the footprint radius. Furthermore, since the TX is partially illuminated, the size of the panel is adjusted through the footprint radius. For example, the equivalent footprint radii for a $N \times N$ antenna array used in [13] is here $w \approx 0.5Nd$, where d is the horizontal and vertical dimension of each antenna element. The beam-tracking process is as follows. The TX uses the two codewords of the first level to divide the area into two sectors. The RX estimates the received power with each beam, finds the beam with the highest power, and sends that information to the TX. The TX then finds the corresponding codeword, estimates the direction of the RX based on that information, and generates beams with the two higher level codewords that correspond to the codeword of the previous level. The RX again finds the beam with the highest power and sends that information to the TX, which then estimates the direction of the RX based on the corresponding codeword. This process is repeated until the highest codebook level is reached. In each level, the codebook has 2^{l_t} codewords, where $l_t = 1, 2, \dots, L_t$ is the current codebook level, and L_t is the number of codebook levels. As a result of the hierarchical process, the total number of codewords that are used to scan the entire area, is $2L_t$ codewords, while in conventional exhaustive search it is 2^{L_t} .

B. Phase 2: Ranging

The ranging process also follows a hierarchical approach with a binary tree-structured codebook. The first step is to generate the binary tree-structured codebook for beam-focusing, which will be used to generate focal areas at the desired distance and with the desired size. To do that, the area of interest is divided in two areas, and each area is then divided in two smaller areas. This process is repeated until the desired resolution is reached, which is also the major radius of the focal areas, r_{max} . Similar to the codebook in Phase 1, the number of focal areas per codebook level, is equal to 2^{l_r} , where $l_r = 1, 2, \dots, L_r$ is the current codebook level, and L_r is the number of codebook levels. The focal distances for the focal areas whose weights are stored in the codebook are calculated as

$$d_f(l_r, i) = \frac{d_f(1, 1)}{2^{l_r-1}} m_i, \quad (7)$$

where $d_f(1, 1) = d_0/4$ is the focal distance with the first codeword in the first codebook level, d_0 is the maximum distance in the area of interest from the TX,

and $i = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{l_r}$ is the codeword index. Moreover, $m_i = 1, 3, 5, \dots, M$ is a set of 2^{l_r} numbers that contains all the odd numbers from 1 to $M = 2^{l_r+1} - 1$. The major radii of the focal areas are calculated as

$$r_{max}(l_r) = \alpha \frac{d_0}{2^{l_r-1}}, \quad (8)$$

where $\alpha \in [0.25, 0.5]$ is the overlapping factor of the focal areas. With $\alpha \leq 0.25$, two adjacent focal areas are formed with zero overlap in their 3-dB threshold (3-dB focal areas). With lower values, there are gaps between the 3-dB focal areas, while with higher values the 3-dB focal areas begin to overlap. With values higher than 0.5 more three or more focal areas begin to overlap. In the case where the RX is inside two 3-dB focal areas, the algorithm can choose either one and continue estimating the TX-RX distance. Moreover, the 3-dB focal areas are designed for $\theta_r = 0$, and when $\theta_r \neq 0$, θ_r they are generated along the directions estimated in Phase 1, with the same d_f , and r_{max} as with $\theta_r = 0$. In [12] it was shown that the focal areas become larger with $\theta_r > 0$, which results in high ranging errors in Phase 2. This is more pronounced in the lower levels of the codebook, where the focal areas are large. This means that when the whole codebook to estimate the TX-RX distance, the errors that appear in the lower levels, due to the enlargement of the focal areas, are transferred to the higher levels. On the other hand, when using only small focal areas, these errors are suppressed.

IV. MOBILE USER LOCALIZATION

In the previous section, the process of estimating the location of the user was described in a manner of exhaustive search with the binary tree scanning process. This method however is not suitable for tracking the location of mobile users, where localization has to be performed frequently and fast. Therefore, to adjust the localization algorithm to the mobile user scenario, the aforementioned algorithm fills the role of the initialization process which takes part in the first three timeslots, while in the next timeslots, the algorithm is simplified by predicting the next location of the user, assuming linear motion, using the estimations in the first three timeslots. Then the TX scans a small area around the predicted location using fewer codebook levels in both phases. The algorithm is presented in Algorithm 1 assuming that starting from the fourth timeslot, the TX utilizes the five highest ($l_t = L_t - 4$) codebook levels.

V. PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT

In this section, the performance of the algorithm is evaluated with Monte-Carlo simulations of 10^5 random motions. The random motions follow curved trajectories that are sampled at the timeslots as shown in Fig. 3. If the number of timeslots is low, then the prediction may not be accurate enough, and the algorithm can fail to

Algorithm 1 Localization and tracking algorithm.

```

t = 1
T: last timeslot
while t ≤ T do
  if t ≤ 3 then
    l_t = 1: Starting beam-forming codebook level.
    S_t = [1, 2^{l_t}]: beam-forming codewords to use.
    l_r = 1: Starting beam-focusing codebook level.
    S_r = [1, 2^{l_r}]: beam-focusing codewords to use
    p'(t) = [0, \frac{d_0}{2}]: Assumes the RX location is in
    the broadside of the TX.
  else
    l_t = L_t - 4
    S_t = [2c_t - 1, 2c_t]
    l_r = L_r
    S_r = [2c_r - 1, 2c_r]
    p'(t) = \frac{p^{(t-1)} + p^{(t-3)}}{2}: Predicted RX location.
  end if
  while l_t ≤ L_t do: Phase 1
    Scan around p'(t) using S_t codewords of the
    l_t-th codebook level.
    Estimate the received power at the RX with
    each beam according to Eq. (2).
    Estimate the direction of the RX, \theta_{RX} based
    on the beam with the highest power at the RX.
    Find codeword, c_t, of the estimation.
    l_t = l_t + 1
  end while
  while l_r ≤ L_r do: Phase 2
    Scan around p'(t) using S_r codewords of the
    l_r-th codebook level.
    Estimate the received power at the RX with
    each focal area according to Eq. (2).
    Estimate the TX-RX distance, d_{RX} based on
    the focal area with the highest received power the RX.
    Find the codeword, c_r, of the estimation.
    l_r = l_r + 1
  end while
  p(t) = [d_{RX} \sin(\theta_{RX}), d_{RX} \cos(\theta_{RX})]: Estimated
  RX location as.
  t = t + 1
end while

```

estimate the correct direction, and therefore, the location of the user. By increasing the number of timeslots, the accuracy of the prediction increases, and the performance of the algorithm is expected to increase. The maximum distance of the users from the TX, d_0 , is 10 m, and their maximum angle in relation to the TX broadside is $\pm 25^\circ$. The central frequency is 150 GHz, the UE antenna gain 20 dB, $\alpha = 0.3$, and the size of the TX (LAA) is considered to be much larger than the beam-footprint on the TX. In Table I, the major radii of the focal areas are shown for each codebook level in Phase

Fig. 3. Example of random motions. The solid curves denote the trajectories, and the markers correspond to the samples that are taken at specific timeslots.

2 for $d_0 = 10$ m, with $\alpha = 0.3$. Unless otherwise mentioned, starting from the fourth timeslot, in Phase 1 the algorithm uses the 5 highest codebook levels, while in Phase 2 only the highest codebook level. Regardless of the algorithm phase, after the initialization process, at the starting codebook level, the algorithm uses four codewords to find the user direction or distance. By using only the highest codebook level to estimate the TX-user distance in Phase 2, the localization errors that are caused by the enlargement of the focal areas when $\theta_r \neq 0$, disappear.

In Fig. 4, the probability of success is presented in (a), and the average localization error in (b), for different codebook (cb) sizes (number of cb levels) and as a function of the number of timeslots where the mobile user localization is performed. In this work, probability of success is defined as the probability that the localization error is lower than the major radius of the last cb level in Phase 2 (see Table I). Moreover, since the prediction is less accurate with fewer timeslots, the algorithm can fail to make an estimation if the power at the RX is below a threshold power level, here set to -90 dBm. Therefore, the average localization error includes only the instances where an estimation was made. Note, that the main cause for high localization errors is the enlargement of the

codebook level	r_{max}
1	3 m
2	1.5 m
3	0.75 m
4	0.375 m
5	0.187 m
6	0.093 m
7	0.046 m

TABLE I
MAJOR RADIUS, r_{max} , OF EACH CODEBOOK LEVEL IN PHASE 2 FOR $d_0 = 10$ M, WITH $\alpha = 0.3$.

Fig. 4. (a) Probability of success of localization, and (b) average localization error for different number of timeslots and codebook levels in Phase 2 for the same motions as in (a). The inset in (a) focuses on a small part of the plot to better show the difference between the codebook sizes, and the dashed lines in (b) show the major radii of the focal areas with the last codebook level.

focal areas when $\theta_r \neq 0$, which is more pronounced in lower cb levels where the focal areas are large. In (a), it is evident that, regardless of the cb size, increasing the number of timeslots increases the probability of success. Moreover, with a large codebook it is harder to estimate correctly the TX-RX distance as starting from the fourth timeslot only the highest cb level is used in Phase 2. This changes with a high number of timeslots. For example, with 3 cb levels, the probability of success at 20, 40, and 60 timeslots, is 92.9%, 99.7%, and 99.9%, with 6 cb levels it is 76.9%, 99.7%, and 99.95%, while with 7 cb levels, it is 57.2%, 95.8%, and 99.65%. In (b), large codebooks in Phase 2 result in lower average localization error as the focal areas are smaller. For example, with 20, 40 and 60 timeslots, the average localization error with 3 cb levels is 38 cm, 31.6 cm and 31.5 cm, while with 7 cb levels it decreases quickly from 50 cm, to 2.3 cm, and 2 cm. For reference, the major radii, marked with dashed lines, are 75 cm with 3 cb levels, and 4.6 cm with 7 cb levels.

Fig. 5 presents the empirical CDF of the localization

Fig. 5. Empirical CDF of the localization error for different number of timeslots for the case with 7 cb levels. The markers show the maximum error in each case.

error with 11 cb levels in Phase 1, and 7 cb levels in Phase 2, for 40, 50, and 60 timeslots. It is shown that increasing the number of timeslots can significantly decrease all localization errors. For example, with 40 timeslots, 99% of all localization errors are lower than 12.7 cm, with 50 timeslots lower than 5 cm, and with 60 timeslots lower than 3.9 cm. Moreover, the maximum localization error with 40, 50, and 60 timeslots is 59.4 m, 18, and 17.4 cm. This shows that increasing the number of timeslots reduces all localization errors as the prediction becomes more accurate, however, after a certain number of timeslots there are diminishing returns.

Fig. 6 shows the importance of the codebook size in Phase 1 in relation to the codebook size in Phase 2, through the probability of success in (a), and the average localization error in (b), as a function of the number of timeslots. Specifically, it is shown that with codebooks of 9–10 cb levels with which the generated beams are wide in relation to the focal areas, the probability of success in (a) is low, at most 30%, and 76.4% respectively. With larger codebooks (e.g. 11 – 12 cb levels) that generate narrower beams, the probability of success reaches 99.6%. It is observed that with few timeslots, the case with 12 cb levels has worse performance than the case with 11 cb levels. The reason for this is that regardless of the codebook size, the same number of codewords is used to scan the area. However, with higher codebook levels the beams are narrower, making it harder to estimate the RX direction. As a result, a smaller area is scanned with the 12th cb level than with the 11th cb level. By increasing the number of timeslots, the prediction becomes more accurate, resulting in the two cases having the same probability of success. This is also reflected in the average localization error in (b). Specifically, the average localization error with 12 cb levels starts from 61 cm with 20 timeslots, decreases to

Fig. 6. (a) Probability of success of localization, and (b) average localization error for different number of timeslots and codebook levels in Phase 1 for the same motions as in (a)

13 cm with 30 timeslots, and is less than 2.5 cm starting with 40 timeslots.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a hierarchical localization algorithm was presented for tracking mobile users. The algorithm takes advantage of beam-forming and beam-focusing techniques to estimate the direction and distance of the user in relation to the TX. To this end, a novel ranging method was presented that takes advantage of the beam-focusing property to concentrate the power of a beam to the desired area. The performance of the algorithm was evaluated through the probability of success, the average localization error, and the CDF of the localization error for different number of timeslots. The results show that with sufficient number of timeslots, the algorithm can achieve 99.6% probability of success, with an average localization error of 2 cm, and 99% of the localization errors below 4 cm.

REFERENCES

- [1] Z. Wei, H. Qu, Y. Wang, X. Yuan, H. Wu, Y. Du, K. Han, N. Zhang, and Z. Feng, "Integrated sensing and communication signals toward 5G-A and 6G: A survey," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 10, no. 13, pp. 11 068–11 092, 2023.

- [2] O. Kanhere and T. S. Rappaport, "Millimeter wave position location using multipath differentiation for 3GPP using field measurements," in *GLOBECOM 2020 - 2020 IEEE Global Communications Conference*, Dec 2020, pp. 1–7.
- [3] S. Fan, Y. Wu, C. Han, and X. Wang, "Siabr: A structured intra-attention bidirectional recurrent deep learning method for ultra-accurate terahertz indoor localization," *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 39, no. 7, pp. 2226–2240, July 2021.
- [4] M. El-Absi, A. Alhaj Abbas, A. Abuelhajja, F. Zheng, K. Solbach, and T. Kaiser, "High-accuracy indoor localization based on chipless RFID systems at THz band," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 54 355–54 368, 2018.
- [5] Y. Lu, Z. Zhang, and L. Dai, "Hierarchical beam training for extremely large-scale MIMO: From far-field to near-field," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 72, no. 4, pp. 2247–2259, April 2024.
- [6] S. Hu, F. Rusek, and O. Edfors, "Beyond massive MIMO: The potential of positioning with large intelligent surfaces," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 66, no. 7, pp. 1761–1774, April 2018.
- [7] C. Huang, G. C. Alexandropoulos, C. Yuen, and M. Debbah, "Indoor signal focusing with deep learning designed reconfigurable intelligent surfaces," in *2019 IEEE 20th International Workshop on Signal Processing Advances in Wireless Communications (SPAWC)*, July 2019, pp. 1–5.
- [8] H. Zhang, H. Zhang, B. Di, K. Bian, Z. Han, and L. Song, "Metalocalization: Reconfigurable intelligent surface aided multi-user wireless indoor localization," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 20, no. 12, pp. 7743–7757, Dec 2021.
- [9] J. He, A. Fakhreddine, C. Vanwysberghe, H. Wymeersch, and G. C. Alexandropoulos, "3d localization with a single partially-connected receiving ris: Positioning error analysis and algorithmic design," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 72, no. 10, pp. 13 190–13 202, Oct 2023.
- [10] S. Droulias and A. Alexiou, "Reconfigurable intelligent surface: an angular spectrum representation approach," in *Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems, and Computers*, 2022.
- [11] S. Droulias, G. Stratidakis, and A. Alexiou, "Near-field engineering in RIS-aided links: Beamfocusing analytical performance assessment," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 29 536–29 546, 2024.
- [12] G. Stratidakis, S. Droulias, and A. Alexiou, "Near-field hierarchical localization for integrated sensing and communication," *IEEE Access*, pp. 1–1, 2025.
- [13] A. Sayeed and N. Behdad, "Continuous aperture phased mimo: Basic theory and applications," in *2010 48th Annual Allerton Conference on Communication, Control, and Computing (Allerton)*, Sep. 2010, pp. 1196–1203.